

Knowledge Distillation-Driven Federated Learning as a Service for Resource-Constrained Edge Intelligence

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Abstract. Federated Learning as a Service (FLaaS) enables large-scale, privacy-preserving training across heterogeneous edge devices but incurs significant deployment and communication overhead when distributing high-capacity models. This paper introduces the integration of *server-side knowledge distillation* into FLaaS, producing compact student models that are deployed for federated training and inference. Distillation is implemented as a configurable service within the FLaaS orchestration layer and operates offline prior to federated training, preserving existing client-side logic. Experiments on CIFAR-10 show that FLaaS+KD reduces model transmission size by 88.8% and deployment energy by nearly 90%, at the cost of an approximate 21% reduction in accuracy. These results demonstrate that centralized KD enables scalable, energy-efficient, and privacy-preserving deployment in resource-constrained federated and edge environments.

Keywords: Federated Learning as a Service · Knowledge Distillation.

1 Introduction

Federated Learning (FL) enables decentralized clients to collaboratively train Machine Learning (ML) models while keeping raw data local, making it key for privacy-preserving learning on edge and mobile devices [15, 7]. However, as model complexity and the number of participating clients grow, FL systems face severe communication and deployment bottlenecks, particularly when distributing large global models to resource-constrained devices [20, 14, 2].

Federated Learning as a Service (FLaaS) [9] provides a service-oriented framework that orchestrates large-scale federated training across heterogeneous mobile devices. By abstracting communication, aggregation, and client coordination behind a unified control layer, FLaaS enables scalable and privacy-compliant deployment of FL across multiple applications and devices [8].

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Knowledge Distillation (KD) [5, 16, 3] compresses high-capacity models (*teachers*) into lightweight ones (*students*) by transferring their semantic behavior rather than their parameters. This produces compact models that retain competitive accuracy while reducing the model size, making KD well suited for deployment and communication-efficient learning in federated settings. [13, 3].

Motivation. However, as model sizes increase, FLaaS must also address deployment-time communication and inference costs, which are often overlooked in training-centric FL systems. Distributing large global models to edge devices incurs significant bandwidth and energy overheads, particularly in swarm and multi-agent environments. Despite this, existing FLaaS frameworks lack integrated mechanisms for lightweight model deployment.

Contributions. We integrate server-side KD into FLaaS through an *offline distillation phase*, producing lightweight student models for federated training and inference. The proposed design operates entirely at the system level, preserving standard FL workflows and client-side logic while enabling automated model compression and deployment. Experiments on CIFAR-10 show that FLaaS+KD reduces model size by 88.8% and transmission energy by nearly 90%, substantially improving deployability across heterogeneous edge environments. FLaaS-KD is released as open-source to facilitate reproducibility and further research[‡].

2 Related Work

Federated Learning Foundations. FL enables multiple decentralized clients to collaboratively train a shared global model while keeping raw data localized and private [7]. Classical FL algorithms, such as FedAvg [15], rely on the iterative exchange of model parameters between clients and the server, aggregating updates to produce a refined global model. Although this paradigm preserves privacy at the data level, it suffers from high communication costs, especially when applied to deep architectures [18].

Knowledge Distillation and Model Compression. KD [5], transfers the knowledge of a large teacher model to a smaller student network by aligning their output distributions. KD has since become a key technique for deploying compact yet accurate models on devices with limited resources [3], providing significant gains in inference efficiency, latency, and energy consumption. These properties make KD well suited to edge intelligence where training large models requires high communications and inference costs.

Federated Knowledge Distillation. The intersection of FL and KD has produced a class of algorithms referred to as Federated Knowledge Distillation (FKD) [12]. Early works, such as FedMD [11], trained models by exchanging logits instead of full model parameters, reducing communication costs. Other works, including ensemble-based schemes [6] and training frameworks such as FedGKT [4], decoupled client and server to support heterogeneous devices. However, these methods typically perform KD *during* the federated training process. Instead, our *system* layer integration targets the pretraining phase.

[‡]<https://github.com/TianyueChu/FLaaS-Server>

3 System Design

3.1 FLaaS Architecture

Legacy FLaaS. The FLaaS architecture [8] comprises four modules: (i) the *admin interface* for configuration and experiment management (model, rounds, etc.); (ii) the *global server*, orchestrating rounds and aggregating client updates; (iii) the *notification and coordination service* that synchronizes clients; and (iv) the set of *mobile clients* that train locally via the FLaaS Software Development Kit (SDK). This modular design enables cross-application participation, multi-tenancy, and heterogeneous devices while keeping client-side logic unchanged.

Extending FLaaS with KD. We extend FLaaS with a server-side KD module integrated into the orchestration layer. During project registration, users specify teacher and student architectures together with KD hyperparameters via the admin interface. The global server invokes the KD sub-module which loads the pretrained teacher, executes the distillation stage on a server-held buffer, and outputs a distilled student head, which is the initial global model used in the standard FLaaS round workflow. This integration preserves the federated learning pipeline while extending the server-side model preparation pipeline (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: **FLaaS+KD workflow.** 1. Offline KD from a server-side teacher to a student head. 2. federated training of the student head on N clients with a frozen backbone. 3. deployment of the trained head to edge devices for inference.

3.2 Knowledge Distillation in FLaaS

Split Model. In the following, we adopt a generic split model $f(\cdot) = h(g(\cdot; \psi); \theta)$ where the *feature extractor* $g(\cdot; \psi)$ is shared and *frozen* on devices, while only the *classifier head* $h(\cdot; \theta)$ is trained; ψ and θ denote the parameters for the feature extractor and the classifier head, respectively.

Student and Teacher Models. We denote by $f_T(x) = h_T(g(\cdot; \psi); \theta_T)$ the (pretrained) *teacher* and by $f_S(x) = h_S(g(\cdot; \psi); \theta_S)$ the (untrained) *student model*. The pretrained global *teacher* $f_T(\cdot) = h_T(g(\cdot; \psi); \theta_T)$ serves as the high-capacity source from which a smaller, resource-efficient *student* head is distilled.

Data. The KD step is entirely centralized and does not involve federated client data. Let $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_s, y_s)\}_{s \in [S]}$ denote a generic dataset, where x_s denotes a feature vector, y_s denotes a label from a finite set, and S is the dataset size. Before the FL phase, the server reserves a centralized *held-out buffer* $\mathcal{D}_{\text{buf}} \subset \mathcal{D}$.

KD Training. The student is trained to match the teacher’s softened output distribution using the standard KD objective [5]. Let $z_T(x)$ and $z_S(x)$ denote the teacher and student *logits*, i.e., the pre-softmax outputs of their classifier heads. We define the corresponding softened class-probability vectors $p_T^{(\tau)}(x) = \text{softmax}(z_T(x)/\tau)$, $p_S^{(\tau)}(x) = \text{softmax}(z_S(x)/\tau)$, where $\tau > 0$ is a temperature parameter. The KD loss combines two components: (i) a standard cross-entropy term (\mathcal{L}_{CE}) that aligns the student with the ground-truth label, and (ii) a Kullback-Leibler divergence term (KL) that aligns the student’s softened predictions with those of the teacher. Following [5], the objective minimized over the student parameters θ_S is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}} = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{buf}}} \left[(1 - \beta) \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(y, p_S^{(1)}(x)) + \beta \tau^2 \text{KL}(p_T^{(\tau)}(x) \parallel p_S^{(\tau)}(x)) \right],$$

where $\beta \in [0, 1]$ balances the relative weight of hard and soft supervision. The teacher weights θ_T remain frozen at this stage; only the student head is updated.

Deployment. After distillation, the student replaces the teacher as the deployable global model and is distributed to clients for both federated training and inference, reducing deployment-time communication and latency.

3.3 Federated Learning in FLaaS

FLaaS* [8] orchestrates the federated training phase between the server and a set of N clients, indexed by $i \in \{1, \dots, N\} \triangleq [N]$. The training follows the standard federated learning phases [15], as described next.

Model. We reuse the split model $f(\cdot) = h(g(\cdot; \psi); \theta)$ introduced in Sec. 3.2, with a shared, frozen feature extractor $g(\cdot; \psi)$ on devices and a trainable classifier head $h(\cdot; \theta)$. At the beginning of federated training, we set the global head to the distilled student parameters, i.e., $\theta \leftarrow \theta_S$. For notational simplicity, we omit the student subscript in the remainder of the FL phase and write θ instead; this corresponds to the student head obtained from the KD stage.

Data. Starting from the dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_s, y_s)\}_{s \in [S]}$ and the KD buffer \mathcal{D}_{buf} defined in Sec. 3.2, we partition the remaining samples $\mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_{\text{buf}}$ across clients. Each client i holds a private subset $\mathcal{D}_i \subset \mathcal{D} \setminus \mathcal{D}_{\text{buf}}$ that never leaves the device.

Federated Learning. At each communication round $t \geq 1$, the server selects a fraction C out of N clients as the set $\mathcal{N}_t \subseteq [N]$, where \mathcal{N}_t denotes the set of participating clients at round t . The server broadcasts the current head parameters θ_t to these clients. Each client i initializes $\theta_{i,i}^{(0)} \leftarrow \theta_t$ (superscripts (\cdot) denote local epoch) and performs E local epochs over mini-batches $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{D}_i$ to minimize

*Although FlaaS supports cross-app training, in the following, we describe the method for a single-app training scenario for simplicity. The methods can be easily generalized to the cross-app training scenario (see [8]).

over mini-batches $\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{D}_i$ to minimize $F_i(\theta) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_i|} \sum_{(x,y) \in \mathcal{D}_i} \ell(h(g(x; \psi); \theta), y)$, where ℓ is the local cross-entropy loss and the feature extractor $g(\cdot; \psi)$ is *frozen* on device. More precisely, each client performs gradient descent steps indexed by $e = 0, \dots, E - 1$ (with weight decay λ_t , step size η) on \mathcal{B} as $\theta_{t,i}^{(e+1)} = \theta_{t,i}^{(e)} - \eta \left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{(x,y) \in \mathcal{B}} \nabla_{\theta} \ell(h(g(x; \psi); \theta_{t,i}^{(e)}), y) + \lambda_t \theta_{t,i}^{(e)} \right)$. After E epochs, every client returns $\theta_{t,i} \leftarrow \theta_{t,i}^{(E)}$ and the server aggregates as $\theta_{t+1} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}_t} \frac{|\mathcal{D}_i|}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_t} |\mathcal{D}_j|} \theta_{t,i}$.

4 Experimental Setup

Evaluation Objective. We evaluate server-side KD within FLaaS. The main evaluation objectives are: (i) to verify that KD produces a compact student model suitable for on-device training and inference; and (ii) to demonstrate that FLaaS-KD reduces communication and energy costs.

Task and Datasets. We use CIFAR-10 [10] with a non-IID Dirichlet split ($\alpha = 0.5$) across $N = 10$ clients. Each client holds 150 training samples; the server reserves 5,000/1,000 samples for KD train/evaluation.

Fig. 2: Student and teacher architectures. The MobileNet base (`bottleneck.tflite`) remains frozen on device, while the lightweight head (`train_head.tflite`) is trained locally and uploaded each round.

Model Architectures. We instantiate the split model from Sec. 3 as presented in using the Fig. 2:

- **Teacher** $f_T(\cdot; \theta_T)$: a `VGG_19` model [19] pretrained on CIFAR-10 (loaded via `torch.hub` [1]), used only during the server-side KD training stage to distill the student model described next.
- **Student** $f_S(\cdot; \theta_S)$: a `MobileNetV2` backbone [17] initialized from ImageNet-pretrained weights, followed by a *single* dense (linear) head and softmax. The backbone is frozen; KD trains the head centrally on the server, and the resulting student is broadcast at the start of federated training.

On-Device Training in FLaaS. Each client executes a split model using the `transfer_api` built on TensorFlow Lite. The frozen MobileNetV2 backbone is packaged as `bottleneck.tflite`, while the trainable dense head is provided as `train_head.tflite` together with `optimizer.tflite` and `inference.tflite`.

(a) Student train/test accuracy (left axis) (b) Transmission energy [mJ] for different and temperature schedule τ (right axis). network scenarios.

Fig. 3: Experimental results for (a) KD training and (b) transmission energy.

During FL rounds, clients update the head weights only, consistent with the split-model design described in Sec. 3. The implementation therefore transmits only the head parameters each round.

Federated Configuration and KD Parameters. We emulate $N = 10$ Android clients with $E = 20$ local epochs (SGD: $m = 0.9$, $B = 20$, $\eta = 3 \times 10^{-3}$) and FedAvg aggregation [15]. KD uses linear τ annealing ($3.8 \rightarrow 1.0$) and $\beta = 0.3$.

5 Results and Discussion

We evaluate the integration of centralized KD within FLaaS along three axes: (i) offline KD training performance, (ii) model compression and deployment efficiency, and (iii) system-level resource usage.

5.1 KD Training

Figure 3a shows the training and test accuracy of the distilled student across KD epochs. The final student reaches a test accuracy of $\approx 71.9\%$, compared to 93.39% for the VGG19 teacher. This corresponds to a trade-off of approximately 21.5 percentage points in accuracy for an almost $9\times$ reduction in model size and the associated communication and energy savings.

5.2 Energy Consumption Analysis

As shown in Fig. 3b, downloading the distilled student model consumes under 12% of the energy required for the teacher across all evaluated network regimes (*low*, *typical*, and *high* throughput). In the typical throughput setting, energy consumption drops from ~ 329.3 mJ to ~ 36.8 mJ, quantifying the deployment-time savings enabled by KD.

5.3 Model Compression and Transmission Efficiency

Table 1 reports server-side profiling metrics for the teacher and KD student including number of parameters, Wall Time, Central Processing Unit (CPU) time, Average CPU utilization, Peak Resident Set Size (RSS) and energy consumed. These values refer to the full models that must be distributed to devices when a new global model is deployed or refreshed. The teacher contains 20,565,834 parameters (78.5 MB), while the KD student contains 2,236,682 parameters (8.76 MB), yielding an 88.8% reduction in model size. This reduces deployment-time download duration by 65%, CPU time by 95%, average CPU load by 82%, and peak RSS by 32%. Since FLaaS exchanges only the head during federated rounds, KD primarily reduces the cost of deploying and updating global models.

Table 1: Server-side profiling for teacher and KD student models.

Model	Parameters	Wall Time [s]	CPU Time [s]	Avg CPU [%]	Peak RSS [MB]	Energy [mJ]
Student	2,236,682(8.76MB)	1.522	0.210	18.6	345.31	36.75
Teacher	20,565,834(78.53MB)	4.354	4.443	102.5	508.22	329.38

5.4 Latency and Scalability

With total round time expressed as $T_{\text{round}} = T_{\text{train}} + T_{\text{upload}} + T_{\text{download}}$, download can dominate when distributing large models. Replacing the teacher with the KD student reduces T_{download} roughly by $|\theta_S|/|\theta_T|$, consistent with Table 1.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper introduced the integration of *server-side knowledge distillation* into the FLaaS framework, enabling lightweight model deployment in federated learning without modifying client-side logic. By performing KD centrally and offline prior to federated training, FLaaS+KD produces compact student models suitable for efficient on-device training and inference. Experiments on CIFAR-10 demonstrate that the distilled student achieves competitive accuracy ($\approx 72\%$) while reducing model size by nearly $9\times$ and transmission energy by almost 90%. These results highlight the suitability of centralized KD for scalable, communication-aware deployment in edge and swarm-based federated systems. Future work includes adaptive teacher-student coordination, dynamic distillation schedules, multi-teacher extensions, and tighter integration with privacy-preserving mechanisms such as differential privacy and secure aggregation.

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